

**EPIDEMIOLOGY AND RESULTS OF TREATMENT OF ESOPHAGODAL-
GASTRIC BLEEDING IN THE ARIDA ZONE OF CENTRAL ASIA USING THE
EXAMPLE OF KHOREZM REGION**

Atanazar Niyazmetov

**Doctor of Medical science, docent of the Department General Practitioner of the
Urgench branch of Tashkent Medical Academy**

Annotation. For a clinician, in light of the latest advances in hematology, the most significant possibility is probably a differentiated etiological approach to the diagnosis and treatment of liver diseases. And this, despite the fact that in a wide variety of etiological processes, the liver may be the only or main target, causing significant uniformity in the main pathological reactions. In this sense, the old saying “Qui bene diagnostit, bene curat” retains its meaning and can only be supplemented in our time by “Qui bene et tempore diagnostit, bene curat” - “Whoever diagnoses well and in a timely manner treats well.” It is well known that liver cirrhosis is a stage of hepatopathy. Its definition is purely pathological and quite definite: restructuring of the entire structure of the liver due to the development of fibrosis and nodular regeneration (D. Alagille, 1982). The lobular structure, as well as the vascular system, is disorganized; over time, this restructuring leads to portal hypertension.

Key words: diseases, fibrosis, nodular, etiological, vascular system

Introduction. Most liver diseases can lead to the development of cirrhosis. Among them, diseases of viral etiology, such as viral hepatitis, dominate in the Central Asian region. According to the literature (Loginov A.S., 1987), cirrhosis of viral etiology is the outcome of chronic active hepatitis of viral etiology, accounting for 50-55% of all patients with chronic hepatitis. Much less often it is the outcome of chronic persistent hepatitis. Slowly evolving through the stages of a chronic disease, the pathological process in the liver within five years ends with the formation of cirrhosis in 0.8-1.0% of patients who have had a symptomatic or anicteric form of viral hepatitis type A or B. In rare cases, cirrhosis develops immediately after an acute viral hepatitis hepatitis, bypassing the stage of chronic hepatitis.

Previously, it was generally accepted that cirrhosis is most often diagnosed in people over 40 years of age (Agzamkhodzhaev S.S., 1971), and for the formation of liver cirrhosis after hepatitis a period of 1-20 years is necessary (Andreev G.N. et al., 1994). However, due to a

number of unfavorable circumstances characteristic of the Central Asian region, especially its arid zone, the high incidence of viral hepatitis in early childhood and the relatively more rapid formation of liver cirrhosis significantly changed the age composition of patients towards rejuvenation (Nazyrov F.G., 1997, Aliev M.M., 1999). Patients with cirrhosis significantly younger than 40 years old are admitted to hospitals with clear manifestations of complications of PG (Abdurakhmanov M.M., 1997). The further course of the disease can be long-term, slowly progressing, or it can be short-lived and galloping. Moreover, the features of the development and progression of a particular complication and the life expectancy of patients are largely determined by the etiological factor, the stage at which the diagnosis was made, the degree of activity of the process, and the adequacy of the treatment provided. The average life expectancy of a patient with CP, according to long-term observations of 501 patients, is 8.56 years (Khazanov A.N., 1997). Taking the activity of the pathological process as a basis, the same author obtained the following indicators of the average life expectancy of patients with cirrhosis. With a subacute course it was 5.5 months, with a rapidly progressing course - 2.69 years, with a slowly progressing course - 7.53, with a sluggish course - 10.3 and with a latent course - 12.25 years. More than 80% of all diagnosed cirrhosis are active (Loginov A.S., Blok Yu.E., 1987).

Methodology. Based on these extremely unfavorable figures from world statistics and following the rule of the ancient saying “Qui bene diagnostit, bene curat”, in this chapter we analyzed the age structure and dynamics of patients with acute and chronic forms of viral hepatitis, officially registered in medical institutions of the Khorezm region, then, taking into account that it is these diseases that most often and most likely lead to the formation of cirrhosis of the liver, we carried out in the same area an analysis of the structure and dynamics of patients admitted to medical institutions in the same area with bleeding from the upper floor of the gastrointestinal tract.

The Khorezm region with a population of 80 thousand people (2983) is located in the low-lying desert plain in the lower reaches of the Amu Darya. According to the geomorphological classification of climates, the region belongs to a zone with arid climatic conditions - with a dry climate, high temperature conditions, low, up to 100 mm per year, amount of precipitation, with a large area of deserts and semi-deserts.

Hepatitis is a common disease in this area. Along with the frequency, it is necessary to point out, in general, the benign nature of the disease: indeed, spontaneous recovery from acute hepatitis is observed in the vast majority of cases, even if the patient did not go to a medical institution not only for inpatient, but even for outpatient care. This factor, as well as the

predominance of anicteric forms, and the lack of strict compliance with mandatory notification of the disease, make us consider the available figures to only partially correspond to reality.

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Conclusions As follows, the intensive incidence rate of acute viral hepatitis, calculated per 100 thousand population of the Khorezm region, in the five-year period (1985-1989) was the most unfavorable. It was 1.5 times higher than the average of the previous 10 years and 3.3 times higher than the average of the next decade (1990-1999). Only based on the results of this comparative analysis, taking into account the average recognized time frame for the formation of liver cirrhosis over 1-20 years (Andreev G.N et al., 1994) after an acute form of hepatitis, a possible reduction in these terms to 10 years in the harsh climatic conditions of the Khorezm region should be expected a significant increase in the number of patients with formed liver disease since the first years of the new millennium. Temperature regime, low, up to 100 mm per year, amount of precipitation, with a large area of deserts and semi-deserts. Hepatitis is a common disease in this area. Along with the frequency, it is necessary to point out, in general, the benign nature of the disease: indeed, spontaneous recovery from acute hepatitis is observed in the vast majority of cases, even if the patient did not go to a medical institution not only for

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